

ISic4081

I.Sicily inscription 4081

Language

Ancient Greek

Type**Material****Object****Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334607

1. [Θεοῖς Κα]ταχθο-
2. [νίοις] vacat
3. [— — Τ] ρυφέρα
4. [ἔζησε (vel sim.)] ἔτεσι #⁵⁶ μ' #⁵⁶
5. [— — —] ΝΕΠΩΤΙ#⁷ [. 1-2.]
6. [— — —]ΗΡ [— — —]
7. [— — — — — — —]
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 334607

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 50.1012.7

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